

ASSESSING FAILURE AND DELAMINATION GROWTH IN COMPOSITES AND BONDED JOINTS UNDER VARIABLE AMPLITUDE LOADS

R. Jones¹, Anthony J. Kinloch², John G. Michopoulos³, Athanasios P. Iliopoulos⁴, Nam Phan⁵, Kishan Goel⁶, Jim Lua⁷, Daren Peng⁸

¹ Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Monash University, Clayton, Victoria, 3800, Australia. Email: rhy.jones@monash.edu

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Imperial College London, Exhibition Road, London SW7 2AZ, UK. Email: a.kinloch@imperial.ac.uk

³ Computational Multiphysics Systems Laboratory, Code 6394, Center for Materials Physics and Technology, US Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, DC 20375, United States. email: john.michopoulos@nrl.navy.mil

⁴ Computational Multiphysics Systems Laboratory, Code 6394, Center for Materials Physics and Technology, US Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, DC 20375, United States. Email: athanasios.iliopoulos@nrl.navy.mil

⁵ Structures Division, Naval Air Systems Command, Patuxent River, MD 20670, United States. Email: nam.phan@navy.mil

⁶ Structures Division, Naval Air Systems Command, Patuxent River, MD 20670, United States. Email: kishan.goel@navy.mil

⁷ Global Engineering and Materials, Princeton, NJ 08540, United States. Email: jlua@gem-innovation.com

⁸ Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Monash University, Clayton, Victoria, 3800, Australia. Email: daren.peng@monash.edu

Keywords: CMH-17-3G, Delamination growth, Fatigue threshold, Bonded joints,

ABSTRACT

Composite and bonded aircraft structures are currently designed such that any delamination/disbond will not grow. However, it is now known that despite this design limit, delaminations and disbonds can both arise and grow when subjected to operational flight loads. In this context in 2009, the FAA Advisory Circular 20-107B introduced a slow growth approach to certification, and this approach is now included in the Composite Materials Handbook CMH-17-3G. To meet the challenges inherent in a slow growth design, this paper summarises selected advances in the state of the art for assessing the effect of damage in composite and bonded airframes. The problem of how to account for the scatter seen in delamination growth is first discussed, and a methodology for determining valid upper bound curves is outlined. Examples that illustrate shortcomings in the current building block approach to aircraft certification are also briefly discussed, and the need for coupon tests to be performed under realistic multi-axial stress states is highlighted. It is also shown that the failure loads predicted using the A4EI computer code, the industry standard approach for determining the failure load of axially loaded bonded joints, and finite element analysis yield very similar failure loads. It is then demonstrated that growth equations that express da/dN in terms of ΔG should not be used to compute crack growth under variable amplitude loads, and an example is presented that illustrates how the Hartman-Schijve equation can be used to accurately compute delamination growth under a variable amplitude load spectra.

1 INTRODUCTION

While carbon fibre epoxy composites have several advantages for use as aircraft structural materials; they are prone to a fairly wide range of defects and damage that have the potential to

significantly reduce residual strength [1-4]. Furthermore, as noted by the US Government Accountability Office [4], there are also concerns about how composite airframe structures behave when damaged, and as they age. Of the various types of defects, delaminations (i.e., single, or multiple internal cracks [1-2, 6-7]), impact damage, and disbonds arising in service are probably the most insidious because they can cause significant reductions in compressive strength [1-9] and are difficult to detect. These concerns are highlighted by the problem of disbonding that arose in the boron epoxy doublers on RAAF F-111 aircraft [10], and disbonding and delamination that arose in US Navy [11] and RAAF F/A-18 inner wing lap splice joint (IWSLJ) [11-13], see Figure 1.

Current approaches to the design and assessment of composite and bonded airframes are based on a building block approach, see Figure 2. In this context MIL-STD-1530D [14] states ... “The building block test program shall include sufficient testing to characterize the effects of material, processing, and manufacturing variability...”. However, as shown in [10], the way in which the building block approach, as outlined in CMH-17-3G [2] and JSSG2006 [15], is commonly implemented cannot be relied upon to ensure against delamination/disbonding in-service aircraft [10]. As a result, the building block test program should include multi-axial tests where the specimens are subjected to realistic (in-service) loads, and (if possible) representative operational environments. Furthermore, as per MIL-STD-1530D [14], which states that the role of testing is to validate and correct the analysis, and as per [13] the development of analytical tools that can account for the inherent scatter in delamination/disbond growth is essential.

Figure 1. Adhesive failure and delamination damage in a US Navy aircraft, from [10].

Figure 2. The FAA/MIL-STD-1530D/CMH-17-3G building block approach, courtesy of R. Wanhill.

To help clarify the current status of failure load computation approaches, the present paper focuses on three topics, viz:

- i) The ability of A4EI [16], which is an extension of the analytical solution given in [17], and standard finite element analysis to accurately determine the failure loads associated with the cohesive failure of axially loaded bonded multi-step lap joints.
- ii) The “no growth” design philosophy outlined in CMH-17-3G and the related fatigue thresholds.
- iii) How to compute delamination growth under a variable amplitude load spectra.

2 THE FATIGUE THRESHOLD MANIFOLD AND THE NEED FOR MULTI-AXIAL TESTING

To be consistent with CMH-173G, JSSG 2006 and MIL-STD-1530D, the fatigue thresholds should be established with sufficient margins to ensure that damage growth due to repeated loads will not occur. However, since under flight loads, the stress state is multi-axial this raises the following questions, viz:

- a) How can uni-axial tests capture the variability in the fatigue thresholds associated with these complex multi-axial (and hence mixed mode delaminations) in-flight stress states?
- b) How can uni-axial tests determine the variability in the growth rates associated with these complex multi-axial (and hence mixed mode delaminations) in-flight stress states?

Whereas for metallic components the variability in the crack growth rates associated with da/dN versus ΔK tests performed in accordance with the test protocol as described in the main body of the test standard ASTM E647-13a is relatively small, the variability in the da/dN versus ΔG curves seen for delamination growth in composites is large. This is aptly shown in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 presents a range of $R = 0.1$ da/dN versus G_{max} curves for IM7/977-3 that were obtained in four different studies [18-21], together with the mean- 3σ upper bound curve determined in [22]. Figure 4 presents a range of $R = 0.1$ da/dN versus G_{max} curves for IM7-8552 given in [23], together with the corresponding mean- 3σ upper bound curve determined in [22]. For metals, the variability in the fatigue threshold and the fatigue crack growth curve is relatively small. As a result, MIL-STD-1530D suggests using the average da/dN versus ΔK curve. However, as can be seen in Figures 3 and 4 this is not true for delamination growth in composites. As a result, it is best to use a statistically valid mean- 3σ upper bound curve.

It follows from Figures 3 and 4 that the various failure/growth modes that arise due to the multi-axial stress state, and the associated variability (scatter) in their values [22, 24], suggests the existence of a fatigue threshold surface that can be represented as a three dimensional thick shell in a 3-D space spanned by the $(\Delta\sqrt{G_{Ithr}}, \Delta\sqrt{G_{IIthr}}, \Delta\sqrt{G_{IIIthr}})$ bases as depicted in Figure 5. For a given mode mix, the variability in the threshold results in the failure manifold having a (variable) thickness, i.e., the failure envelope can be visualized as a 3D (rather) thick shell rather than a simple surface in 3D space, see Figure 5. The exact shape of this shell threshold can only be determined when experiments with controlled mode mix due to multi-axiality of loading are performed.

Figure 3. Scatter in the delamination growth tests in IM7/977-3 CFRP composite laminates where the DCB tests have been started at G_{max} values which represent various percentages of G_c [15], together with test data presented in [20], [21], and specimens C1_9, C1_11 and C1_19 [18]. The upper-bound FCG rate curve determined in [22] using the Hartman-Schijve approach with a mean value of $\sqrt{G_{max,thr}}$ minus three standard deviations, is also plotted.

Figure 4. Scatter in the delamination growth tests in the IM7/8552 CFRP composite laminate tested at various percentages of G_c [4], together with the predicted upper-bound FCG rate curve determined in [22] using the Hartman-Schijve approach with a mean value of $\sqrt{G_{max,thr}}$ minus three standard deviations.

Figure 5. Schematic representation of the fatigue threshold manifold (thick shell).

At this point, it should be noted that knowing and characterising the variability in the thresholds and the associated delamination growth rates is a key point raised in MIL-STD-1530D. Fortunately, [22, 24-27] have shown that delamination growth can be characterised by the Hartman-Schijve (HS) variant of the NASGRO equation and that the variability in the delamination growth curves is controlled by the variability in the threshold and fracture toughness terms in the HS equation. As a result, it is now possible to obtain a statistically valid estimate of the variability in the fatigue thresholds, see [22, 24]. This methodology has been validated in [28-30]. Whilst it is accepted that for metals the fatigue threshold is a function of the crack length, and the fatigue test standard ASTM E647-13a stresses that for small naturally occurring cracks the threshold is very small, no work can be found on the fatigue thresholds associated with small naturally occurring delaminations.

3 MULTI-STEP LAP JOINTS

Having noted the problems that have recently arisen with (adhesively bonded) multi-step lap joints let us next address the question of how to determine the strength of an axially loaded multi-step lap joint. Bonded joints and bonded step lap joints are used in a number of aircraft, viz: Triton, the F-15 horizontal stabilator, the F/A-18 wing, Super Hornet, Beech Starship and the Lear Fan [3]. Section 10 of CMH-17-3G recommends using the computer program A4EI [16], which is an extension of the double lap joint solution given in [17], for the design of both bonded joints and bonded repairs to damaged composite structure. This computer program, which uses the strain energy density failure criteria [17] to assess the propensity for cohesive failure in the adhesive layer, was first validated, for simple joint configurations, as part of the USAF Primary Adhesively Bonded Structure Program (PABST) [31]. Its ability to accurately predict the failure loads associated with axially loaded complex metal to composite step lap joints was established in [32]. In this context, Section 10.2 of CMH-17-3G states that A4EI can be used to design/assess bonded joints and that this “*avoids the need for elaborate finite element calculations.*” Unfortunately, CMH-17-3G does not give examples where this is shown for a multi-step lap joint. Consequently, in this section, we will show that, provided failure is due to cohesive failure in the adhesive, A4EI and finite element analyses (under specific assumptions associated with the discretization of the relevant models) do indeed yield similar estimates of the load carrying capacity of an axially loaded bonded multi-step lap joint.

To this end, let us consider the axially loaded titanium step lap joint configuration shown in Figure

6. The adhesive was 0.1 mm thick, and the specimen was taken to have a (nominal) width of 100 mm. The adhesive was a toughened epoxy (FM300K), and it was assumed to have an elastic-perfectly plastic stress-strain curve. The mechanical properties of the titanium adherends and the FM300K adhesive are:

Adhesive (FM300K): $G = 393 \text{ MPa}$, yield stress = 39 MPa, maximum shear strain = 0.31, $\nu_{\text{adhesive}} = 0.3$;
 Adherend (Titanium): $E = 110,316 \text{ MPa}$, $\nu_{\text{adherend}} = 0.3$

The results of the non-linear (elastic-plastic) finite element analysis, obtained using NASTRAN, ABAQUS, and COMSOL, and A4EI are presented in Table 1. The mesh used in the NASTRAN analyses is shown in Figure 7. Here we see that A4EI and finite element analyses gave very similar failure loads. (As previously mentioned, failure was assumed to be due to cohesive failure of the adhesive, and failure was assumed to occur when the energy density at the critical point in the adhesive was equal to the NAVAIR value of 10.15 MPa.)

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of the multi-step bonded joint, dimensions are in mm.

Figure 7. Schematic diagram of the multi-step bonded joint, dimensions are in mm

Analysis	FE	A4EI	% Difference
<i>NASTRAN</i>	1874	1872	< 1
<i>COMSOL</i>	1885	1872	< 1
<i>ABAQUS</i>	1842	1872	2.4

Table 1: Predicted failure loads (N/mm)

3.1 Limitations of A4EI

Whilst the above section has established the ability of A4EI to reasonably accurately compute the axial load carrying capacity of adhesively bonded joints, provided that failure is cohesive, the limitations of A4EI need to be noted. These include:

- i. A4EI cannot be used to assess adhesive failure, i.e. interfacial failure.
- ii. A4EI should not be used to assess failure in the composite adherends.
- iii. A4EI has not been validated for multi-step lap joints subjected to shear, or combined axial and shear loads.
- iv. In its current form, A4EI can't be used to assess if under combined axial and shear loads the stresses in the adhesive are beneath their fatigue allowable.
- v. A4EI can't be used to assess fatigue crack growth in the adhesive.

Whilst A4EI can be extended to address point iv), to address failure in the composite adherends requires the use of finite element analysis.

4 DELAMINATION GROWTH

Let us next turn to the question of delamination/damage growth in composite structures. CMH-17-3G suggests that given the "increased scatter" in both strength and fatigue life, special considerations must be applied in fatigue/durability aspects of the design of composites. Note the words "increased scatter." The significance of this "scatter" is also reflected in the statement in CMH-17-3G that whereas testing to 2 lifetimes is sufficient for metallic airframes to obtain the same level of certainty composite airframes should be tested to 14 lifetimes. CMH-17-3G also suggests that the certification of composite and bonded airframes should be based on a building block approach. This raises the following questions:

- a) Given the extensive scatter seen in delamination tests on composites will no (or limited) observable delamination growth in a Full Scale Fatigue Test (FSFT), or building-block tests, that generally do not replicate the actual multi-axial stress state seen in the aircraft, mean that there will be no (or limited) delaminations seen for in-service aircraft?
- b) What happens if, as reported in [10-13], an operational aircraft is found to have a delamination/disbond that did not arise either during the FSFT or in the building-block tests? This could be the case, for example, if peel plies are accidentally left in a composite component, if a hole is mis-drilled, or if the operational usage changes sufficiently over time. In such cases, the results of the FSFT and the building block tests may not be particularly relevant.
- c) What happens if the composite structure is repaired in a manner that was not evaluated in either the FSFT or in the building-block tests?
- d) Furthermore, what happens when the life observed in the FSFT divided by the safety factor (which is often 2) has been exceeded?

References [10-13] revealed that fleet experience shows that the answer to the first question above is 'No'. That is to say: The fact that there is no growth in an FSFT, or the associated building-block tests, does not necessarily mean that delaminations or disbonds will not arise in service. It is anticipated that the answer may be that FSFT and building-block tests are of limited use if they do not replicate the actual multi-axial stress state seen in the aircraft. To definitively answer these questions requires, amongst other things, a capability to predict damage growth.

The previous discussion leads to the question of how to compute delamination growth. Many authors have attempted to express the delamination growth rate (da/dN) as a function of ΔG ($= G_{\max} - G_{\min}$) and G_{\max} , where G_{\max} and G_{\min} are the maximum and minimum values of G in a cycle [18, 33].

However, as shown in [34, 35] this approach often leads to anomalous results which can be alleviated by expressing da/dN as a function of $\Delta \sqrt{G}$ ($= \sqrt{G_{max}} - \sqrt{G_{min}}$)² and $\sqrt{G_{max}}$. To illustrate the ambiguity that arises when expressing da/dN as a function of ΔG consider a delaminated structure tested under repeated block loading. Each load block consists of n_1 cycles at a load level P_1 and n_2 cycles at a load level P_2 such that $P_1 > P_2$. The load amplitude ΔP ($= P_{max} - P_{min}$) is the same for both, see Figure 8, and there are a large number of load blocks to failure. The test (P1) with the higher R-ratio, $R = P_{min}/P_{max}$, has both a higher maximum and a higher minimum load, see Figure 8.

Let us further assume that the da/dN versus ΔG curve is as given by [36], and shown in Figure 9. The da/dN versus ΔG curve suggests that as you move from the block of cycles with a high load P_1 to the block of cycles with the lower load P_2 (with the same ΔG in both cases) and a lower R ratio, then the delamination growth rate would increase dramatically. This is clearly non-physical, and indicates that ΔG does not adequately reflect the crack tip behavior during cyclic loading. Thus, predictions of delamination growth under variable amplitude loading should not be based on a da/dN versus ΔG analyses.

Figure 8. A schematic diagram of a single load block.

Figure 9. The da/dN versus ΔG curve, from [34].

Fortunately [22, 24, 25, 35] have shown that several of the problems discussed above vanish if da/dN is expressed as per the Hartman-Schijve delamination growth equation, viz:

$$da/dN = D[(\Delta\sqrt{G} - \Delta\sqrt{G_{thr}})/(1-\sqrt{(G_{max}/G_c)})^{1/2}]^p, \quad (1)$$

where D and p are constants, G_c is the quasi-static fracture toughness, and ΔG_{thr} is the fatigue threshold. To illustrate this, consider the $R = 0.1$ variable amplitude DCB test reported in [33] for an E-glass vinyl ester resin laminate. Since the da/dN relationship given in [33] expressed da/dN as a function of G , [37] reformulated Equation (1) to take the form:

$$da/dN = D[(\sqrt{G} - \sqrt{G_{thr}})/(1-\sqrt{(G_{max}/G_c)})^{1/2}]^p \quad (2)$$

This yielded $D = 1.13 \cdot 10^{-6}$, $p = 1.8$ and $G_{thr} = 180 \text{ J/m}^2$. As shown in [33], G_c has a strong R curve dependency, increasing from an initial value of approximately 320 J/m^2 to approximately 900 J/m^2 as the delamination length increases. Consequently, when computing delamination growth using Equation (2), [37] used the $G_c(R)$ curve given in [33]. The resultant measured [33] and computed [37] delamination length (a) versus cycles curves are shown in Figure 10. Here it can be seen that the crack length history computed in [37] using Equation (2) is in excellent agreement with the measured experimental data.

Figure 10. Comparison with experimental test data, from [37].

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper has focused on three topics, viz: The ability of the A4EI code, and standard finite element analysis to accurately determine the failure loads associated with the cohesive failure of axially loaded bonded multi-step lap joints, the “no growth” design philosophy outlined in CMH-17-3G, and how to compute delamination growth under a variable amplitude load spectra.

This multi-step lap joint analysis supports the statement in CMH-17-3G that, the A4EI code can be used to assess the axial load carrying capacity of complex bonded joints without the need to perform finite element analysis. An added advantage of using simple finite element tools is that the results,

under certain discretization assumptions, are consistent with the certification basis of the aircraft. By this we mean the results are consistent with A4EI.

The ability of A4EI to accurately predict the cohesive failure of multi-step lap joints under shear, and combined axial and shear loads requires further investigation. Furthermore, given that current bonded structures in operational aircraft have generally been designed in accordance with a ‘no growth’ design philosophy, A4EI needs to be extended to assess if for combined axial and shear loads the adhesive stresses are such that the “no growth” design criteria is satisfied.

The “no growth” design philosophy outlined in CMH-17-3G for composite structures is also discussed, and the large scatter in the fatigue threshold is highlighted. In this context fleet experience has shown that despite passing the building block test programs that are currently used to establish no growth, delamination and disbond growth can still arise in operational aircraft. It is suggested that to overcome this, the building block test program needs to include tests under representative multi-axial flight loads. It is also shown that the variability in fatigue performance leads to the fatigue threshold being a thick shell rather than a simple surface. It is suggested that this threshold surface and the associated variability is best determined using a multi-axial test facility.

The slow growth approach to certifying delaminated structures is also discussed. In this context it is advocated that delamination growth equations that express da/dN in terms of ΔG should not be used to compute crack growth under variable amplitude loads. An example is then given that illustrates how the Hartman-Schijve equation can be used to accurately compute delamination growth under a variable amplitude load spectra.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

John Michopoulos and Athanasios Iliopoulos acknowledges support for this work by the Office of Naval Research (ONR) through the Naval Research Laboratory’s core funding. Rhys Jones and Daren Peng acknowledge support via an Office of Naval Research (ONR) NICOP Grant N62909-19-1-2011-P00001.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. A. Baker, R. Jones, R. J. Callinan, Damage tolerance of graphite/epoxy composites, *Composite Structures*, 4, 1985, pp. 15-44.
- [2] R. Jones, R. J. Callinan and A. A. Baker, Residual strength of impact damaged composites, *Int. J. Fracture*, 24, 1984, R51.
- [3] CMH-17-3G, *Composite Materials Handbook, Volume 3: Polymer Matrix Composites Materials Usage, Design and Analysis*, Published by SAE International, March 2012.
- [4] E. Demuts, R. S. Whitehead, R. B. Deo, Assessment of damage tolerance in composites, *Composites Structures*, 4, 1985, pp. 45-58.
- [5] AVIATION SAFETY - *Status of FAA's Actions to Oversee the Safety of Composite Airplanes*, United States Government Accountability Office, GAO Report to Congressional Requesters, GAO-11-894, September 2011.
- [6] R. Jones, S. C. Galea, J. J. Paul, *Assessment of impact damage in composite structures*, Defence Science and Technology, Aeronautical Research Laboratory, Technical Report 23, 1993, www.dtic.mil/dtic/tr/fulltext/u2/a277063.pdf
- [7] E. T. Camponeschi, Jr., *Compression of Composite Materials: A Review*, David Taylor Research Center, DTRC-87050, November 1987, <http://www.dtic.mil/dtic/tr/fulltext/u2/a189272.pdf>
- [8] R. L. Ramkumar, *Compression fatigue behaviour of composites in the presence of delaminations*, *Damage in Composite Materials*, ASTM STP 775, 1982, pp. 184-210.
- [9] D. S. Saunders, G. Clark, Fatigue damage in composite laminates, *Materials Forum*, 17, 1993, pp. 309 – 331.
- [10] L. Molent, R. Jones, *The F111C wing pivot fitting repair and implications for the design/assessment of bonded joints and composite repairs*, Chapter 10, pp. 511-543, *Aircraft Sustainment and Repair*, Edited by R. Jones, N. Matthews, A. A. Baker and V. Champagne Jr., Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann Press, 2018, ISBN 9780081005408.

- [11] E. M. Mueller, S. Starnes, N. Strickland, P. Kenny, C. William, The detection, inspection, and failure analysis of a composite wing skin defect on a tactical aircraft, *Composite Structures*, 145, 16, 2016, pp. 186-193.
- [12] C. Kourloufas, J. Wittkopp, *F/A-18A/B Inner Wing Bonded Joint Defects - Through Life Management Strategy*, ADF Aircraft Structural Integrity Symposium (AASIS16), 16th-18th November, 2016, available on line at <http://www.defence.gov.au/DASP/ConferencesAndSeminars/Presentations.asp>
- [13] D. Slater, *Inner Wing Step Lap Joint (IWSLJ) Research Program*, NAVAIR Composites Workshop, Monash University, 3rd December, 2018.
- [14] MIL-STD-1530D, 2016, Department of Defense Standard Practice; Washington, DC, USA, 2016.
- [15] Department of Defense Joint Service Specification Guide, Aircraft Structures, JSSG-2006, October 1998.
- [16] L. J. Hart-Smith, *Design Methodology For - Bonded-Bolted Composite Joints*, Vol. II. User Manual and Computer Codes, Technical Report AFWAL-TR-81-3154, February 1982.
- [17] L. J. Hart-Smith, 1973, *Adhesively bonded double lap joints*, NASA Langley Research Center Report NASA CR-112235, January 1973.
- [18] G. B. Murri, Effect of data reduction and fiber-bridging on Mode I delamination characterization of unidirectional composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 48, 2014, pp. 2413-2424.
- [19] S. Stelzer, A. J. Brunner, A. Argüelles, N. Murphy, G. Pinter, Mode I delamination FCG in unidirectional fibre reinforced composites: development of a standardized test procedure, *Composite Science Technology*, 72, 2012, pp.1102-1107.
- [20] K. Hoo., E. V. Iarve, M. Braginsky, E. Zhou, D. H. Mollenhauer, Progressive Failure Simulation in Laminated Composites under Fatigue Loading by Using Discrete Damage Modeling, *AIAA SciTech Forum, 57th AIAA/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, 4th-8th January 2016, San Diego, California, USA*, AIAA 2016-0726.
- [21] M. J. Donough, A. J. Gunnion, A. C. Orifici, C. H. Wang, Scaling parameter for fatigue delamination growth in composites under varying load ratios, *Composites Science and Technology*, 120, 2015, pp. 39-48.
- [22] R. Jones, A. J. Kinloch, J. G. Michopoulos, A. J. Brunner, N. Phan, Delamination growth in polymer-matrix fibre composites and the use of fracture mechanics data for material characterisation and life prediction, *Composite Structures*, 180, 2017, pp. 316-333
- [23] G. B. Murri, Evaluation of Delamination Onset and Growth Characterization Methods under Mode I Fatigue Loading, Langley Research Center, Hampton, Virginia, *NASA/TM-2013-217966*.
- [24] L. Yao, R. Alderliesten, R. Jones, A.J. Kinloch, Delamination fatigue growth in polymer-matrix fibre composites: A methodology for determining the design and lifing allowables, *Composite Structures*, 96, 2018, pp. 8-20.
- [25] R. Jones, S. Stelzer, A. J. Brunner, Mode I, II and mixed Mode I/II delamination growth in composites, *Composite Structures*, 110, 2014, pp. 317-324.
- [26] T. Chocron and L. Banks-Sills, *Nearly Mode I Fracture Toughness and Fatigue Delamination Propagation in a Multidirectional Laminate Fabricated by a Wet-Layup*, Physical Mesomechanics, 22, 2, 2019, pp. 107-140. Pleiades Publishing, Ltd., 2019, ISSN 1029-9599.
- [27] L. Simon, L. Banks-Sills, V. Fourman, Mode I delamination propagation and R-ratio effects in woven composite DCB specimens for a multi-directional layup, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 96, 2017, pp. 237-251.
- [28] A. J. Brunner, S. Stelzer, G. Pinter, G.P. Terrasi, Cyclic fatigue delamination of carbon fiber-Reinforced polymer-matrix composites: Data Analysis and Design Considerations, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 83, 2016, pp. 293-299.
- [29] A. J. Cano, A. Salazar, J. Rodríguez, Evaluation of different crack driving forces for describing the fatigue crack growth behaviour of PET-G, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 107, 2018, pp. 27-32.

- [30] M.Y. Shiino, F.M.G. Ramírez, F.P. Garpelli, N.N.A. da Silveir, R.C.M. Sales, M.V. Donadon, Interlaminar crack onset in co-cured and co-bonded composite joints under mode I cyclic loading, *Fatigue and Fracture of Engineering Materials and Structures*, 42, 3, 2019, pp. 752-763, 2019.
- [31] D.L.Potter, *Primary Adhesively Bonded Structure Technology (PABST), Design Handbook for Adhesive Bonding*, Technical Report AFFDL-79-3129, Final Report, 15 March 1977, 14th January 1979.
- [32] E. B. Birchfield, R. T. Cole, L. F. Impellizzeri, *Reliability Of Step-lap Bonded Joints*, AFFDL-TR-75-26, 1975.
- [33] H. Chen, K. Shivakumar and F. Abali, A comparison of total fatigue life models for composite laminates, *Fatigue Fract Engng Mater Struct*, 29, 2006, pp. 31-39.
- [34] C. Rans, R. Alderliesten, R. Benedictus, Misinterpreting the results: How similitude can improve our understanding of fatigue delamination growth, *Composites Science and Technology*, 71, 2011, pp. 230-238.
- [35] R. Jones A. J. Kinloch, W. Hu, Cyclic-FCG in composite and adhesively-bonded structures: the FAA slow crack growth approach to certification and the problem of similitude, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 88, 2016, pp. 10-18.
- [36] K. Tanaka, H. Tanaka, Stress-ratio effect on mode II propagation of interlaminar fatigue cracks in graphite/epoxy composites, *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture*, 6, 1997, pp. 126-142.
- [37] R. Jones, J. G. Michopoulos, A. J. Kinloch, A. P. Iliopoulos, D. Peng, N. Phan and J. Lua, Damage Assessment In Composite And Bonded Airframes, *Proceedings AIAC 2018: 18th Australian International Aerospace Congress, Melbourne, Australia, 24 – 28th February*, Published by Engineers Australia, Royal Aeronautical Society, 2019, pp. 301-306,, available at <https://search.informit.com.au/fullText;dn=322095245985832;res=IELENG>